

D Level Language Reference

(Extended)

Abstract

I've expanded the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) by adding two more levels, D1 and D2, to further illustrate language proficiency. These new levels aim to explore language complexity beyond the existing CEFR standards.

Here's a summary of the new levels D1 and D2 as extensions to CEFR:

D1: Full Expert

Individuals at this level are adept at comprehending and mastering every literary work in the given language. Typically, professionals in this category might include writers, language experts, or journalists.

D2: Software or AI

This level doesn't pertain to a human individual but refers to a software or artificial intelligence entity. Represents a comprehensive database encompassing all possible words and phrases within the specified language.

While not a human proficiency level, it denotes a comprehensive repository of the language's vocabulary and expressions, typically embodied in a software or AI system.

Conclusion

These additional levels aim to delve deeper into language proficiency beyond what's covered by the existing CEFR levels. They address specialized expertise and technological capabilities, acknowledging the diverse realms of language mastery and the incorporation of artificial intelligence in language processing and comprehension.

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